

Table 1: Official Advice Codebook (Merged).

Category	Codes	Definition or example
Transaction Safety	Check before transaction	Details to check before transaction like UPI ID, amount, receiver details
	Check after transaction	Details to check after transaction like message from the bank, account balance, logout is once done
	Process for sending money	Enter UPI PIN or scan QR code only to send money not receiving
Valid Sources of Information	Avoid public sources	Avoid public helpline, devices, wi-fi networks available
	Use official sources	Always use official websites, apps, helpdesks, browsers
Reporting Issues	Always contact official helpdesk	To report issues always contact bank or UPI official helpdesk
	Report fraud/scam calls	Always report the contacts of any fraud/scam calls
	Report unauthorized transactions	Report if there were any unauthorized transactions
Sharing and Sensitive details	Never share confidential details online/public	Don't share user devices, PINs or Passwords, personal details
	Avoid saving sensitive details on phone	Never save card details and banking details on phone
	Don't share sensitive details with banks/customer support	Don't share any personal details via calls, emails, or text messages
Safety Measures on Devices	User account safety	Enabling 2-factor authentication, block scam contacts
	PIN/password safety	Keep mobile and UPI PIN different, have strong PIN/Passwords
	Device safety	Have strong device and app locks, safeguard SIM, don't leave mobile unattended
Safety Measures for Transactions	Account safety	Create strong PIN, set a reminder to change PIN, block account after suspicion, check login time
	Device safety	Avoid publicly available devices, jailbroken and rooted devices for transactions
	Transaction safety	Reject suspicious requests, enable security shield, beware of phishing, UPI frauds, transact privately
Keep up-to-date	Transaction check	Check alerts from banks and providers, transaction history and PINs regularly
	Account check	Check bank statements, USSD requests, monitor app permissions and updating apps regularly

Category	Codes	Definition or example
	Device check	Update device regularly
Security Steps	PIN/password security	Change PIN after suspicion, don't enter a PIN in public, memorize PIN don't write it anywhere
	App security	Enable necessary permissions in apps, read reviews of apps, download apps from official sources
	Transaction security	Check promotional and transactional messages, don't be negligent towards transactions
	Device security	Be cautious of Bluetooth and GPS features, enable broadband connectivity if only necessary
	Account security	Check URLs, set up alerts, manage own accounts, don't allow browser remember account details
Avoid Unknown Situations	Scams and risks	Avoid unknown guidance, requests, merchants, urgency, distractions, demands etc
	User data security	Avoid unknown calls, emails, attachments, links, websites, social media interactions etc
	Device and app security	Avoid unknown charging ports, SIM cloning, swapping, auto-connect wi-fi networks etc